

Statistical significance

All correlations highlighted in Tables 2–4 and noted in this study are statistically significant at a Bonferroni-corrected significance level of 0.05. Statistical significance for a correlation coefficient evaluates only whether the correlation coefficient can be distinguished from zero. That might happen because the correlation coefficient is large, but it can also happen because the sample size is large. In other words, a large sample size can allow you to demonstrate that a tiny correlation coefficient is non-zero (statistically significant), which is not a scientifically interesting result. As such, although we want to be sure that the correlation coefficients are statistically significant (non-zero), once we do so we want to focus on the size of the correlation coefficients, as done in this paper.

There is a simple relationship between a correlation coefficient, sample size, and statistical significance, which can make it unnecessary to run separate statistical tests for every correlation coefficient. Because the statistical significance of a correlation coefficient is calculated through a t-score, it is possible to determine a critical t-score for statistical significance, given the sample size (n) and the significance level (α).

```
n <- 300
alpha <- 0.05
qt(p=alpha/2, df=n-2, lower.tail=FALSE) # alpha/2: 2-tailed test

## [1] 1.967957
```

From this, we know that any t-score more extreme than 1.968 will be statistically significant at the 0.05 level when sample size is 300. Using this, it is possible to calculate the critical value of the correlation coefficient that is statistically significant for a given sample size. When the null hypothesis is that the correlation is zero (no correlation), the t-score is calculated as

$$t = r / sr$$

where sr is the standard error of the r , given by

$$sr = \sqrt{(1-r^2) / (n-2)}$$

The critical value of the correlation coefficient for a given sample size and significance level can therefore be calculated as follows:

```
r <- seq(0.0001, 0.9999, 0.0001)
alpha <- 0.05
n <- 300
t <- r / sqrt((1-r^2) / (n-2))
cutoff <- qt(p=alpha/2, df=n-2, lower.tail=FALSE)
r[max(which(t<cutoff))]
```

```
## [1] 0.1132
```

This shows that if n is 300, any correlation coefficient that is larger than 0.1132 is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Squaring the final line of code will give us the critical R-squared.

```
r <- seq(0.0001, 0.9999, 0.0001)
alpha <- 0.05
n <- 300
t <- r / sqrt((1-r^2) / (n-2))
cutoff <- qt(p=alpha/2, df=n-2, lower.tail=FALSE)
r[max(which(t<cutoff))]^2 # squared

## [1] 0.01281424
```

Any r-squared larger than 0.0128 will be statistically significant at the 0.05 level when $n=300$.

When many correlations are calculated, we wish to avoid type I errors (accepting false null hypotheses). A common but highly conservative approach is the Bonferroni correction, accomplished by dividing the significance level by the number of statistical tests (312 in this study). This increases the critical value of r-squared, making it more difficult to reject the null hypothesis.

```
r <- seq(0.0001, 0.9999, 0.0001)
alpha <- 0.05
nComparisons <- 312
alpha <- alpha/nComparisons # Bonferroni correction
```

```

n <- 300
t <- r / sqrt((1-r^2) / (n-2))
cutoff <- qt(p=alpha/2, df=n-2, lower.tail=FALSE)
r[max(which(t<cutoff))]^2

## [1] 0.04674244

```

Because there are 312 tests in this study, r-squared must now be greater than 0.0467 to achieve statistical significance at a Bonferroni-corrected 0.05 level, when n is 300.

This critical value decreases as n increases. For example, if n is 400, the critical value of the Bonferroni-corrected r-squared is 0.035, and if n is 500 the critical value is 0.028. Knowing this can save us much effort. For example, if we have calculated the critical value for a sample of a given size (say, n=300), any r-squared larger than this for any sample this size *or larger* will also be statistically significant.

The sample sizes in this study are (sorted from smallest to largest): 66, 284, 302, 380, 384, 414, 417, 423, 429, 477, 540, 540, 540, 544, 545, 551, 554, 558, 560, 561, 561, 561, 562, 563, 566, 568. Note that all but three are equal to or larger than 380. For 380, the critical value of r-squared is 0.037; therefore, any value of r-squared that is larger than 0.037 for a sample of size 380 —*and all the larger samples*— is statistically significant.

The tables in the main manuscript highlight only those values of r-squared that are considered to be substantial (greater than 0.10, that is, 10% of the variance). These are all comfortably larger than the critical value of 0.037 and are easily statistically significant. Some values in Tables 2–4 are statistically significant, but they are smaller than the cutoff of 0.100. Although they are statistically significant, these r-squareds are so small as to be of little scientific interest because they indicate that little of the variance in community composition is explained by elevation, distance to the coast, or latitude. They are statistically significant because sample size is large, not because the correlations are important.

The three smaller samples (n=66, 284, and 302) have critical values are 0.201, 0.049, and 0.046. Their values are highlighted in the main manuscript tables only if they are greater than 10% and if they are also statistically significant (confidently non-zero).